

List of Enabled Devices

List of devices transferring data to Chemotion ELN

The following list summarizes those devices for which a transfer routine from the devices to Chemotion ELN was enabled. For most of the devices, a detailed description of the routine is given in the link (last column of the table). If the description is missing, we will provide it soon. If you have questions, please don't hesitate to contact us directly. We are constantly working on the integration of new devices, please let us know if you need support for your favorite devices.

There are several approaches for the automatic transfer:

- transferring data through the **email provider**
- **exe** running as a program
- **powershell script** running as a background service
- **macro**

On the other hand, manual transfer means that the device is not connected to any network and therefore, one manual transfer step is needed. This is usually solved via a direct regular upload of data collections to the Chemotion ELN data exchange server.

Device Type	Vendor	Model	Software	File type	Data Transfer process
GC/MS	Agilent	6890 GC / 5973N MSD	MSD ChemStation E.02	.D folder	ChemStation Macro (details)
GC/MS	Shimadzu	GC-2030 / MS-QP2020	LabSolutions 4.53SP1	.gcd->.cdf (MS AIA +others)	exe (details)
GC	Shimadzu	Nexis GC-2030	LabSolutions 5.110	.gcd -> .cdf (AIA +others)	exe (details)
HPLC	Agilent	1100	LC ChemStation B.04	.D folder	ChemStation Macro (details)
LC/MS	Agilent	1100 HPLC / 1100 MSD	MSD ChemStation B.04	.D folder	ChemStation Macro (details)
LC/MS	Agilent	1260 HPLC /	OpenLab	.srlt-> .cdf	exe (details)

		IQ MS	CDS 2.6	(AIA +others)	
SEC	Agilent / PSS	1200 HPLC	PSS winGPC		exe (details)
LC/MS	Shimadzu	LC-40 / LCMS-2020	OpenLab CDS 2.6	.lcd -> .cdf (AIA +others)	exe (details)
MS	Advion	expression-L CMS	Mass Express	.datx -> .cdf	exe (details)
MS	ThermoFisher	MAT95	xCalibur	.raw	manual
NMR	Bruker	Avance 400	TopSpin or IconNMR	_.zip -> _.dx	email (details)
NMR Benchtop	Magritek	60 Proton Ultra	Spinsolve		<u>automatic backup function</u> (details)
FTIR	Bruker	Alpha II	Opus 8.6	.dpt	exe (details)
FTIR	Bruker	Alpha II	Opus 8.5	.0 -> .dx	exe (details)
Raman	Bruker	MultiRAM	Opus 6.5	.0 -> .dx	exe (details)
UV-VIS	Horiba	Duetta	EzSpec		exe
DSC	Netzsch	DSC 214	NETZSCH Messung		exe (details)
DSC	TA Instruments	DSC2500	TRIOS	.tri -> .csv, .xls, .xml	exe (details)
TGA	TA Instruments	TGA5500	TRIOS	.tri -> .csv, .xls, .xml	exe (details)
EIS	BioLogic	VMP-300	EC Lab	EC-Lab raw data binary file(.mpr)	exe (details)
Potentiostat	Gamry	1010	Framework		exe
Microscope	Leica	STELLARIS 5	Application Suite X	.jpeg	exe (details)